

PEDAGOGICAL IMPORTANCE OF FORMING CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, the purpose of the pedagogical study of the creative process is to create a creative environment, creative climate, creative groups, and create favorable pedagogical and psychological conditions for the creative person. There are thoughts about the step-by-step study of the creative process.

Keywords: pedagogue, psychologist, creativity, creativity, person, child, person, parent, educator, teacher, family.

Creativity is not the creation of some kind of object or artistic work, but the ability to approach each task from its own point of view, to be able to think independently about a problem, to be able to connect all the knowledge gained during the study to the events in life and to use them. We need to understand that he can analyze, express his new views on the studied field. It is necessary to pay special attention to the development of students' ability to express their thoughts in writing. Because, through this, students express their knowledge more fully and meaningfully. Through independent study, students should also pay attention to their speaking. Because the role of oral speech in education is incomparable.

If we look at the history of mankind, the birth of each child from the mother is not a natural-biological phenomenon, but it is born with buds of certain abilities. These abilities are formed by parents as responsible persons in the family, and by educators and teachers in the society. As the child grows up, it would not be wrong to say that his abilities are formed through the activities of various teams in the educational process.

As the society develops, the need to educate mature and well-rounded individuals also increases. This, in turn, imposes huge tasks on expert trainers and experts. Humanity works in various spheres of society. The individual tries to contribute to the development of the industry through his abilities and creativity.

The study of creative pedagogy opens the way to the discovery of talents, the development of inventors and, in turn, to scientific and social progress. The purpose of pedagogically studying the creative process is to create a creative environment, a creative climate, creative groups, and create favorable pedagogical and psychological conditions for the creative person. As a result of the step-by-step study of the creative process, only the unique, characteristic aspects of the human mind are revealed. Each stage of creativity is a complex process that provides information about the needs, values, emotions and intellect of a creative person. Many scientists have expressed their opinions about creativity, including:

Professor M. Makhmudova, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, says about creativity: "Consequently, they pay attention to the fact that creativity can be manifested only in the conditions of purposeful work of an individual." [1]

M. Solakhutdinova "The development of a person as a creative person is genetically determined and manifested. Therefore, a person acts as a creative subject from childhood. "Creativity" means creativity of a person and is characterized by the type of creative activity of a person in any field" [3].

The above points show that creativity is interpreted differently by everyone. Creativity is the activity of a person to create new material and spiritual blessings. Human thinking, perception, memory, imagination, attention, and will actively participate in creativity. Creativity is determined by the richness of imagination in these students. Imagination predicts what is imagined. Imagination is the mental reconstruction of the image of things and events perceived by a person. Imagination can be divided into the following types:

- visions;
- auditory hallucinations;
- olfactory perceptions;
- skin sensations.

Imaginations are similar to perception and arise on the basis of perception. Buds of creativity appear in people on the basis of imagination. In fact, creativity does not depend on age, but on the ability and imagination of a person. We should not forget to appreciate creative people and create opportunities and conditions for them. Because creative people are the creators of news that affects our society.

Here are the instructions for the formation of creative activity in students:

- making friends with books;
- increase intellectual potential;
- formation of individual abilities;
- visit and participate in exhibitions in museums, art and galleries;
- being able to use information and communication technologies;
- to be aware of world news, exchange ideas, etc.

In order for the work to be creative, it is necessary to show the characteristics of perseverance and hard work. Many people think that it is only a question of ability, that talented people are engaged in creativity without difficulty, that everything will happen to them by itself. In reality, even talented people can't create anything if they don't work hard.

Difficulties should not be avoided in any work. A person matures in the process of overcoming difficulties, his spiritual and physical strength is strengthened. Hard work alone is not enough for creativity. Appropriate abilities are also necessary, which (if a person shows the necessary will and interest in work) develop in the course of activity. The process of creativity transitioning from one form to another is considered a new pattern of rules, a drawing, a new type of certain structures. Newly created forms are new interpretations of old forms. As soon as the rules are created, the creative person begins to create new rules based on them.

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process of creative work, there is a special mental state that can be called or accepted as inspiration. Inspiration is characterized by a person's spiritual powers and abilities being extremely elevated. Thanks to this, work becomes very effective, special valuable thoughts arise, necessary words are found, and the entire process of gathering all one's thoughts is done easily and quickly. In doing so, he experiences joyous feelings of satisfaction from his work.

Any type of work that manifests itself in initiative, creates something innovative, makes good changes to the work process, acquires a creative character. Creativity is the original solution of a labor task or the creation of a new material or spiritual product that has a social value of activity. Inventing machines, making various suggestions in production, creating works of art, musical works, applying new original methods that ensure the success of work (engineer, doctor, teacher, worker's work) can be the subject of creativity.

In order for work to have a creative character, it must first be an idea that a person can follow. It requires a great interest in creative work and doing it as well as possible. A person's knowledge and his ability to think about what he is doing plays a very big role here. In this case, relying on the facts, it is possible to determine something new or create something original.

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